

Motivating Work for Ethnic Minorities: Case Study of Tuyen Quang, Vietnam

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Abstract:

The article has synthesized theoretical models of motivation, motivating employees. In additionally, the article analyzes the factors affecting employees' work motivation. From the analysis of the current situation of job creation and labor situation of ethnic minority people in Na Hang, Tuyen Quang, Viet Nam. We propose solutions to motivate people working for ethnic minorities in Na Hang district, Tuyen Quang Province, Viet Nam

Keywords: Motivation for work, ethnic minorities, Na Hang

1. Introduction

Once job satisfaction has been achieved, employees will have a more positive work motivation, which in turn leads to higher productivity and efficiency. The problem with businesses to achieve satisfactory goals for employees is to learn and study the factors affecting the work motivation of employees in their enterprises. From that, it is recommended to have a suitable research model. The study of the model of factors affecting the work motivation of direct employees plays a very important role and will have practical applications.

The northern mountainous district of Tuyen Quang province, Na Hang district has 46,000 people with 12 ethnic groups living, of which ethnic minorities account for 89.3%. Employment settlement for ethnic minorities has been identified as an important task in the local poverty reduction. In order to create jobs for ethnic minorities, it is better first to motivate them to work for them.

In this paper, the author discusses factors affecting employees' work motivation, analyzing the situation of job creation and motivating ethnic minorities in Na Hang and proposing solutions to help motivate ethnic minorities in Na Hang.

2. Literature review and theories

2.1. The concept of motivation and motivation for employees

According to Vroom (1964), motivation is a state of the formation when workers expect that they will receive the results and rewards as they wish if they try to do the job.

According to Mitchell (1982), he said: Motivation is a level that an individual wants to reach and choose to align his behaviors.

According to Robbins (1993), Motivation is the willingness to promote the organization's best efforts, provided that the organization must be able to meet some individual needs.

According to Mullins (2007), Motivation can be defined as an internal incentive that can stimulate individuals to achieve goals to fulfill some needs or expectations.

Motivating work for employees

Labor motivation comes from internal thoughts of workers. Labor motivation is expressed through the specific tasks that each employee is undertaking and in their attitude towards the organization. Each employee undertaking a different job may have different work motivation to work more actively.

It is possible to draw a common understanding of labor motivation: Labor motivation is the internal factors that motivate people to work in conditions that enable high productivity and efficiency actively. The expression of motivation is readiness, effort, passion for work to achieve the organization's goals as well as the employees themselves.

The issue of labor motivation for human resources in general and for employees in organizations in particular has been interested in research by many scientists. It can be understood that creating labor motivation is that administrators use a system of policies and measures to manage employees to motivate employees to work, motivating them to be more satisfied with their work and look forward to contributing to organizations and businesses.

2.2. Theories of labor motivation

There are many theories about labor dynamics, but the doctrine has a general conclusion that increasing motivation for workers will lead to higher employee achievement and greater organizational successes. Basic theories about labor motivation include:

2.2.1. Abarham Maslow's doctrine of needs

Maslow (1960) argues that people with different needs need to be satisfied. He divided the demand system into 5 different groups in order from low demand to higher demand

According to Maslow: Satisfying the needs of individuals starting from the lowest demand, the lower demand is satisfied, the demand is new. Managers want to motivate their employees; managers must first understand where those employees are in the hierarchy of needs, thereby directing their satisfaction to their needs. Motivational policies achieve the highest results.

2.2.2. Study the two-factor theory of Herzberg

This theory is divided into two groups of motivational factors:

- Group of motivating factors: are internal factors of work, creating satisfaction, including personal achievements, status, recognition, work itself, responsibility, and promotion. These are 5 basic needs of employees when participating in the work. The characteristic of this group is that if it is not satisfied, it leads to dissatisfaction. If it is satisfied, it will have a motivational effect.

- Group of maintenance factors: are factors belonging to the working environment of workers, including compensation, policies and management regulations of enterprises, personal relationships with individuals and substance the amount of monitoring, stable work, working conditions, the balance of life and work. These factors, when well organized, will help prevent dissatisfaction with the work of workers.

2.2.3. Stacy Adams' fair doctrine

Equity theory is a theory of employee mobilization introduced by John Stacy Adams, a behavioral and behavioral psychologist in 1963.

The fair doctrine states that workers compare what they put into a job (input) with what they receive from that job (output) and then compare the input-output ratio of them with the input-output ratio of others. If their rate is equal to the rate of others, it is assumed that there is a fair situation. If this rate is not equal, they think there is an injustice.

However, the theory of fairness has not elucidated some issues. For example, how can employees choose people to compare? How can they combine and compare their inputs and outputs and those of others to come to conclusions? On the other hand, fairness or injustice is only relative and depends on the perceptions of individuals and the relationship of individuals with groups and organizations. Although there are unknown

issues, the fair theory is supported by many types of research and suggests to us many important things in the field of labor motivation.

2.2.4. Victor Vroom's expectation theory

Unlike Maslow, Victor Vroom does not focus much on research needs but mainly focuses on research results. V. Vroom's expectation theory is built according to the formula:

Attractive x Expect x Media = Encouragement

Inside:

- Gravity (reward) = attractiveness for a certain goal
- Expectations (work performance) = employee confidence that if working hard, the task will be completed
- Means (beliefs) = employees' beliefs that they will receive a reward for completing the task.

The achievement of these three elements is the encouragement - the power that leaders can use to help their organization fulfill its goals.

This theory of Victor Vroom can be applied in employee management at agencies and businesses. Managers need to plan human resource management so as to clearly show the relationship between effort and achievement, between results and rewards, and create the attractiveness of results and rewards. with workers. When these are done, the employees' motivation will be created.

3. Factors affecting employees' work motivation

Through the basic doctrines of motivation, we can see the elements of work motivation. These factors are factors that affect the work motivation of workers. Applying these theories, several studies have shown factors affecting motivation and motivation in many different perspectives. Specifically,

First, Boeve's research (2007)

Boeve (2007) conducted a study of motivational factors of faculty of assistant physicians in US medical schools on the basis of Herzberg's two-factor theory and descriptive index. work (JDJ) of Smith, Kendall, and Hulin (1969). Accordingly, motivational factors are divided into two groups: internal factors, including the nature of work, opportunities for training and promotion and external factors including salaries, superiors, and support. contact with colleagues.

Second, research by Abby M. Brooks (2007)

Abby M. Brooks (2007) conducted a study by interviewing through a questionnaire consisting of 53 observed variables for 181 people doing different jobs in the United States. The author has proposed the following research model:

The research results indicate that the combination of two factors that set goals and job satisfaction is the best way to predict employees' work motivation; The factors that strongly influence employee satisfaction include: evaluating work performance, training, higher levels, contributing to the organization.

Third, research by Teck-Hong and Waheed (2011)

In the study of Teck-Hong and Waheed (2011), the author proposed a model to study factors affecting work motivation to conduct a survey with salespeople in Malaysia. The results of the analysis have proved that the most important motivation is working conditions, recognition. The evidence concludes that the factors maintain more effective motivating factors in motivating salespeople.

Fourth, research by Marko Kukanja (2012)

Marko Kukanja (2012) studied the factors affecting the work motivation of tourism service employees in the Piran coastal region of Slovenia. The study was conducted with 191 employees working in bars, restaurants, and coffee shops, the results show that salary is the most important factor, followed by social welfare and flexible working time. Active; Training elements are rated the least important.

Fifth, research by Shaemi Barzoki and colleagues (2012)

Shaemi Barzoki et al. (2012) conducted an analysis of the factors affecting the motivation of doctrine based on Herzberg.

According to research by Barzoki and colleagues, there are 7 factors that affect the motivation of the employees proposed by the author, including occupational safety, company policy, relationships with colleagues, supervision. And relationships with superiors, working conditions, personal life, wages, and bonuses.

After studying many studies on motivating work for workers, it can be seen that Herzberg's two-factor theory and Maslow's demand theory are one of the most widely used doctrines currently.

Research on factors affecting work motivation will provide information for managers to determine which factors strongly affect the work motivation of workers, creating a premise to build incentive mechanism encouragement for employees to increase the efficiency of human resource management in enterprises.

4. The situation of motivational work for minority laborers in Na Hang district

In order to create jobs for effective ethnic minorities, Na Hang district focuses on implementing vocational training, counseling and vocational training well; well implement credit policies, employment support, and economic development for ethnic minorities. From the beginning of the year until now, the district has opened 12 vocational training classes for 389 rural workers, costing nearly 791 million VND. 100% of the participants are ethnic minorities.

The district also focuses on directing localities to exploit the potentials and advantages to develop agricultural and handicraft, production models. Currently, Hong Thai commune has built 5 ha of safe vegetables and 24 ha of pear trees. In the communes of Yen Hoa, Da Vi, Sinh Long and Con Lon, to develop soybean and green bean growing models; model of improving Shan tea in Sinh Long, Hong Thai and Son Phu communes; model of cage fish farming in Na Hang hydropower reservoir, model of fattening buffaloes in Nang Kha commune ... The district has developed 3 cooperatives of agriculture, forestry, and fishery. Models have created jobs, contributing to improving income and life for people.

Besides, through programs and projects to support loans for production development, people's incomes are increasingly raised. With the capital of the National Target Program for Sustainable Poverty Reduction and the Rural Construction Program, from 2016 up to now, the whole district has 2,704 households to borrow 14.8 billion VND for economic development. Implementing policies to support product development of the province, the whole district has 567 households borrowing over 30.3 billion VND to buy buffaloes to breed, develop cage fish models ...

In particularly, these economic models are strongly developed in the youth force, creating strong confidence in the positive results to change the local face in the coming time. Union district actively coordinated to organize career counseling for 350 youth union members; transfer of scientific and technical advances to 240 young people, of which the majority are young people from ethnic minorities. The Union has built 14 economic models for high income, 1 model of economic development club, 2 models of young farms. During the year, from the National Fund for Employment of 120, VND 200 million was supported for ethnic minority youth to develop 4 economic models in Hong Thai commune. At the same time, the delegation entrusted with VBSP for 1,146 households to borrow nearly 51 billion VND for economic development.

By the end of October 2018, the whole district has created jobs for 1,455 workers, reaching 92.67% of the set target (1,570 employees). In particular, 90% of workers are ethnic minorities. Thanks to the effectiveness of job creation for ethnic minorities, the district's poverty reduction rate has ensured the plan. According to review and assessment of the situation of poverty reduction in 2018, the poverty rate is estimated to decrease by 3.85%, reaching 100% of the year plan; bringing the poverty rate down to 34.31% in the district.

5. Work motivation solution for minority workers in Na Hang district

Job characteristics are important factors affecting the motivation of ethnic minorities. In order to make the work of ethnic minorities rich, meaningful and important, it is possible to follow some ways:

- Give ethnic minorities' greater freedom in deciding issues such as selecting working methods, the order of work execution and working time within the general provisions of the District.
- Encourage ethnic minority participation in decisions and encourage work coordination.
- Make ethnic minorities feel responsible for their work; show them that their role is important.

In order to create motivation for ethnic minority people, planning, promotion and appointment of cadres are also one of the important factors because it creates a destination in the work schedule and strives of employees.

In addition, the training to improve the capacity and qualifications for ethnic minorities can also make the most of existing resources and improve the effectiveness of the organization. At the same time, the training also helps workers get a deep understanding of the agency's objectives and culture; better understand job requirements, profession, perform your tasks voluntarily.

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